

Conductometric investigations of thorium soaps

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Manuscript received 25 July 2006, revised 18 May 2007, accepted 24 May 2007

Abstract : The conductivity results of thorium soaps showed that these soaps act as weak electrolyte in dilute solution of benzene-methanol mixture. Various thermodynamic parameters for dissociation and association process were evaluated.

Keywords : Thorium soap, conductometry.

In continuation of our work¹ the present paper deals with the conductivity measurements of thorium soaps in benzene-methanol mixture with the aim to evaluate various thermodynamic parameters for the dissociation and micellization process.

Results and discussion

The specific conductance, k of thorium soaps (butyrate, valerate, caproate and caprylate) in benzene-methanol mixture increases with increase in the concentration, temperature and decreasing chain length of the fatty acid constituent of the soap molecule. This increase in the specific conductance may be due to the ionization of thorium soaps into thorium cation, Th^{4+} and fatty acid anion, RCOO^- (where R is C_3H_7 , C_4H_9 , C_5H_{11} and C_7H_{15}) and due to the formation of micelles at higher soap concentration. The plots of specific conductance vs soap concentration for thorium soaps are characterized by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite soap concentration which corresponds to the critical micelle concentration (CMC). The values of the CMC decrease with chain length of soaps but increase with the temperature. The molar conductance, μ of the dilute solution of thorium soaps decreases with increasing soap concentration, may be due to combined effects of ionic atmosphere, solvation of ions and decrease in mobility and ionization with the formation of micelles. The plots of molar conductance, μ vs $C^{1/2}$ are concave upwards indicating that thorium soaps behave as weak electrolyte in dilute solution therefore Debye-Huckel-Onsager's equation is not applicable to these soap solutions.

The ionic concentrations in dilute soap solutions are low and the interionic effects may be negligible. The dilute soap solution do not deviate appreciably from ideal behaviour and the activities of ions may be taken as almost equal to the concentration. The degree of dissociation, α may be replaced by the conductance ratio, μ/μ_0 , where μ is the molar

conductance of finite concentration and μ_0 is the limiting molar conductance at infinite dilution. We have,

$$\mu^4 C^4 = \frac{K\mu_0^5}{256\mu} - \frac{K\mu_0^4}{256}$$

where K is the dissociation constant.

The values of the μ_0 and K can be obtained from the slope, $[K\mu_0^5/256]$ and intercept $[-K\mu_0^4/256]$ of the linear portion of the plots of $\mu^4 C^4$ vs $1/\mu$ (Fig. 1, representation of one system) for dilute soap solution.

From the plots of degree of dissociation, α vs soap concentration, C it is observed that thorium soaps act as weak electrolyte. The values of degree of dissociation, α decreases rapidly with the increase in soap concentration below the CMC, while it decreases slowly above the CMC.

Table I. Values of various factors

Soaps	Temp. (°C)		
	40	50	60
Factors $10^4 \times \text{CMC}$ (g mol dm^{-3})			
Butyrate	6.45	6.65	6.75
Valerate	6.15	6.35	6.50
Caproate	6.10	6.30	6.35
Caprylate	6.00	6.20	6.30
Limiting molar conductance (μ_0)			
Butyrate	1.29	1.40	1.48
Valerate	1.03	1.25	1.40
Caproate	1.02	1.23	1.37
Caprylate	0.99	1.19	1.33
Dissociation constant ($K \times 10^7$)			
Butyrate	2.10	2.00	1.81
Valerate	2.22	2.10	2.00
Caproate	2.35	2.22	2.14
Caprylate	2.65	2.50	2.40

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters for dissociation process and association process

Sl. no.	Soap	ΔG_D^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)			$-\Delta S_D^0 \times 10^2$ (kcal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)			$-\Delta H_D^0$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)
		40 °C	50 °C	60 °C	40 °C	50 °C	60 °C	
1.	Butyrate	40.032	41.445	43.004	3.548	3.543	3.548	1.528
2.	Valerate	39.886	41.311	42.728	3.415	3.415	3.414	1.146
3.	Caproate	39.739	41.165	42.540	3.404	3.403	3.400	1.146
4.	Caprylate	39.417	40.843	42.222	3.346	3.348	3.346	1.042
		$-\Delta G_A^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)			$\Delta S_A^0 \times 10^2$ (kcal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)			ΔH_A^0 (kcal mol ⁻¹)
		40 °C	50 °C	60 °C	40 °C	50 °C	60 °C	
5.	Butyrate	40.660	44.103	45.892	4.327	4.308	4.290	0.995
6.	Valerate	42.107	44.163	46.679	4.388	4.368	4.348	1.137
7.	Caproate	42.178	44.585	47.093	4.413	4.392	4.374	1.194
8.	Caprylate	42.904	45.000	47.187	4.462	4.436	4.417	1.327

The values of the dissociation constant, K change slowly in dilute solutions but show a drift at higher concentration which may be due to the fact that the activity coefficient of the ion are not exactly equal to unity. This deviation in the values at higher concentration may be due to the failure of Debye-Huckel's activity equation at higher concentration. The dissociation constant decreases with increase in temperature which confirms that these soaps in benzene-methanol mixture are exothermic in nature.

Various thermodynamical parameters for the dissociation and association process have been calculated. The dissociation constant and heat of dissociation ΔH_D^0 have the relationship

$$\frac{\partial \ln K}{\partial T} = \frac{\Delta H_D^0}{RT^2}$$

$$\text{or } \log K = \frac{\Delta H_D^0}{2.303 RT} + \text{constant}$$

From the slope of linear portion of the plots of $\log K$ vs $1/T$ heat of dissociation, ΔH_D^0 for thorium soaps in benzene-methanol mixture have been obtained (Table 2). The negativity of these values confirms the exothermic nature of the dissociation process. The values of heat of dissociation decrease with the increasing chain length of the soap. The free energy change ΔG_D^0 for the dissociation process have been calculated using the equation,

$$\Delta G_D^0 = -RT \ln K_D$$

where K_D is dissociation constant. The values of the free energy for the dissociation process per mole of monomer have been calculated and are tabulated.

In the aggregation process counter ions are bound together to form micelles. The standard free energy ΔG_A^0 for the association process is given by the relationship,

$$\Delta G_A^0 = (2 - \beta) RT \ln X_{CMC}$$

where β is calculated from the specific conductance vs

Fig. 1. $\mu^1 C^1$ vs $1/\mu$. Solvent : benzene-methanol mixture thorium butyrate.

concentration plots and is equal to the slope of this plot above CMC divided by the slope of this plot below CMC. X_{CMC} is expressed as a mole fraction and defined as the total number of moles present at the CMC is equal to the sum of moles of the solvent and the surfactant. The values of free energy for the micellization (Table 2), process are higher than the dissociation process which supports micellization.

For the phase separation model the standard enthalpy changes ΔH_A^0 of micellization per mole of monomer is given by the relationship,

$$\frac{\partial(\ln X_{CMC})}{\partial T} = \frac{\Delta H_A^0}{2RT^2}$$

$$\ln X_{CMC} = - \frac{\Delta H_A^0}{2RT} + C$$

The values of ΔH_A^0 have been obtained from the plots of $\ln X_{CMC}$ vs $1/T$ and are tabulated. The values of ΔH_A^0 are positive which indicates that the association process of thorium soaps is endothermic in dilute solution. Association is favoured by the higher values of ΔH_A^0 than ΔH_D^0 .

The values of the standard entropy change for dissociation and association process ΔS_D° and ΔS_A° respectively have been obtained by the equation,

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

The positive values of ΔS_A° and negative values of ΔG_A° for micellization process and the negative values of ΔS_D° and positive values of ΔG_D° for dissociation process indicate that the association process is favoured over the dissociation.

It is, therefore, concluded that the thermodynamics of dissociation and association can be satisfactorily explained by conductivity measurements in the light of phase separation model. The results confirm the exothermic nature of dissociation process and endothermic nature of association process of thorium soaps.

Experimental

All the chemicals used for the preparation of thorium soaps

were of A.R. grade and were purified by standard methods. Thorium soaps were prepared by direct metathesis of the corresponding sodium soaps with the required amount of aqueous solution of thorium nitrate with constant stirring. The precipitated soap was filtered and washed first with distilled water and finally with alcohol. The metal soaps were first dried in an air oven and finally under reduced pressure and further purified by recrystallisation. Thorium soaps were dissolved in benzene-methanol mixture of desired composition and equilibrated to ambient temperature. The conductivity measurements of the solution of thorium soaps in benzene-methanol mixture were made with a digital conductivity meter using dip type conductivity cell with platinized electrodes at different temperatures in a thermostat. The accuracy of the results was $\pm 0.5\%$.

References

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